

(ECL system: Amersham) was used for labeling and detection.

Graphical genotypes of the five lines are shown in the figure. Several chromosome domains originating from each indica donor parent were detected in all lines. We found four domains in Norin PL 2 (chromosomes 5, 11, 12); six in Kanto PL6 (chromosomes 1, 2, 3, 4, 8, 12); seven in Norin PL 5 (chromosomes 1, 3, 4, 8, 9,11); two in Norin PL 6 (chromosomes 3, 11); and one in Aichi 42 (chromosome 6). We also detected two domains (on chromosomes 3 and 11) common to both Norin PL 5 and Norin PL 6. Some undetermined domains

Parental lines resistant to green rice leafhopper.

Line	Cross combination ^a
Norin PL 2 (Kanto PL 3)	Pe-bi-hun /Kanto 98// 2*Kanto 100
Kanto PL 6	Kanto 107/3/ Tadukan /Kanto 98 // Kanto 100 / 4 / Nipponbare
Norin PL 5 (Saikai PL 2)	Reiho/ C203-1 //2*Reiho/3/ Saikai 137
Norin PL 6 (Ou PL 1)	Toyonishiki/ Lepedumai // Ou284/3/2*Toyonishiki
Aichi42	Nipponbare/4/Alchi24/3/Kanto 105//Nipponbare*5/ Rantaj-emas 2

^a Indica varieties from which resistance genes were derived are in boldface. Kanto 98, Kanto 100: Kochikaze/ Nipponbare.

did not show polymorphism between indica donors and the three japonica cultivars. To determine these domains, other japonica varieties in those crosses should be tested further.

Chromosomal regions that remained indica domains of the five parental lines were detected in the study. But because GRLH resistance genes may be located on those domains, we will conduct linkage analysis between resistance to GRLH and RFLP markers in a hybrid population to identify the gene loci.

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RFLP mapping of brown planthopper resistance gene *Bph1* in rice

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The nine brown planthopper (BPH) resistance genes identified so far have not yet been located on the linkage map in detail. In this study, we determined the *Bph1* locus using several restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) markers. BPH-resistant indica variety IR28 (*Bph1*) was crossed with Koshihikari, a susceptible japonica variety. We tested 92 F₃ lines of the cross for resistance in a mass screening using biotype 1 BPH and IR28 and Koshihikari. DNA was extracted from young leaves of the parents and F₃ lines using the cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide method. The RFLP probes, except XNpb, were provided by NIAR/STAFF.

The F₃ lines from the cross Koshihikari/IR28 segregated into 68:24 for resistant homozygous or heterozygous (R+H) and homozygous susceptible (S). Although susceptible lines died after infestation, we could not distinguish between resistant homozygous and heterozygous plants. This segregation showed a good fit to the expected 3(R+H):1 (S) ratio ($\chi^2 = 0.058$).

We initially used several markers located on chromosome 4, based on the study of Ikeda and Kaneda (1983), that reported the location of *Bph1* on chromosome 4 by trisomic analysis. However, our RFLP analysis showed that *Bph1* was not linked to 11 markers on chromosome 4. We then used several RFLP markers located on chromosome 1. The *bph2* gene, allelic or closely linked to *Bph1*, was linked to the *d2* gene on chromosome 4 at a 39.4% recombination value (Ikeda 1985). Ideta et al (1984) reported that *d2* was located on chromosome 1 using RFLP analysis.

Graphical genotypes of five rice parental lines. In each of the 12 chromosomes, the 5 strips stand for, from left to right, Norin PL 5, Norin PL 2, Kanto PL 6, Aichi 42, and Norin PL 6. Each bar beside the strips shows the position of 123 RFLP markers used.

Linkage analysis between *Bph1* and RFLP markers on chromosome 12.

Gene pair AB	Segregation mode in F ₃						c ^{2a}	Recombination value (%)	Genetic map distance (cM)
	A_BB	A_Bb	A_bb	aaBB	aaBb	aabb			
<i>Bph1</i> - G148	20	0	41	1	0	24	10.9 (<0.01)	18.4 ± 10.1	19.3 ± 10.3
<i>Bph1</i> - C185	61	0	5	7	0	17	39.1 (<0.001)	11.5 ± 3.6	11.7 ± 3.6
<i>Bph1</i> - XNpb248	20	42	6	0	4	20	54.5 (<0.001)	10.7 ± 3.4	10.9 ± 3.4
<i>Bph1</i> - XNpb304-1	19	42	6	0	5	19	48.6 (<0.001)	11.9 ± 3.6	12.1 ± 3.6
<i>Bph1</i> - XNpb319	18	42	6	0	5	19	48.6 (<0.001)	11.9 ± 3.6	12.2 ± 3.6
<i>Bph1</i> - XNpb304-2	21	40	6	0	5	19	49.1 (<0.001)	12.1 ± 3.6	12.3 ± 3.6
<i>Bph1</i> - XNpb336	20	38	9	1	6	17	33.0 (<0.001)	18.9 ± 4.5	19.9 ± 4.5
<i>Bph1</i> - XNpb316	21	33	14	2	9	13	12.5 (<0.01)	30.3 ± 5.6	35.2 ± 5.6
<i>Bph1</i> - G124-1	18	36	7	2	14	8	6.6 (<0.01)	32.7 ± 5.9	38.1 ± 6.0

^aCalculated based on the ratio of 3:6:3:1:2:1 (df 2).

However, *Bph1* was not linked to the 21 RFLP markers on chromosome 1. We therefore used several RFLP markers located on the other 10 chromosomes to obtain the marker linked to *Bph1*. The results showed that *Bph1* was linked to G148, C185, XNpb248, and XNpb304-1 on chromosome 12 at recombination values of 18.4, 11.5, 10.7, and 11.9%, respectively (see table). Thus, we conclude that *Bph1* is located on chromosome 12. These loci are arranged as G148 - C 185 - *Bph1* - XNpb248 - XNpb304-1 - XNpb319 - XNpb304-2 (see figure).

However, results of earlier studies (Ikeda and Kaneda 1983, Ikeda 1985) were inconsistent with our findings. Mistakes during trisomic analysis for insect and

disease resistance are possible. Weak and scanty trisomic plants that have the resistance gene may appear susceptible under resistance selection pressure. The recombination value of 39.4% between *bph2* and *d2* is also too distant to confirm a linkage relationship. Previous studies did not use marker genes on chromosome 12. Use of several RFLP markers on all chromosomes enabled us to determine the location of *Bph1* on chromosome 12.

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Arrangement of *Bph1* and RFLP markers on chromosome 12. The genetic distances are given in centimorgan units.

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Stress tolerance—salinity

Principal component analysis and variety classification in relation to rice seedling salinity tolerance

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Salinity is one of the major constraints to rice production in Cuba; improved salt-tolerant varieties are essential for achieving economically important gains in yield. We evaluated the salinity tolerance of some varieties important to rice breeding programs in eastern Cuba.

Distilled water (EC 0.02 dS m⁻¹) was used as the laboratory medium and as a control. Salinity stress (EC 12 dS m⁻¹) was

adjusted by adding NaCl. Twenty seeds were kept in each solution in petri dishes, with five replications. Water volume was maintained by adding solution. Root length, seedling height, and fresh and dry seedling matter were measured after 7 d. Salinity tolerance indexes (STI) were calculated using the equation STI (%) = 100 (IS/IC), where IS is the mean of saline solution indicator and CL is the mean of the control solution indicator.

Principal component analysis showed that more than 83% of the total variability between varieties was accumulated in the first two components (see table). The STI (based on seedling height and seedling dry matter) in the first component and the STI (based on root length) in the second component appear to have the highest value of correlation with the principal axis, indicating the usefulness of these indexes in classifying varietal tolerance.

Results of principal component analysis.

Characteristic ^a	Principal components	
	1	2
STI based on Ht	0.746	0.009
STI based on RL	0.290	0.634
STI based on FM	-0.538	0.281
STI based on DM	0.732	0.010
Eigenvectors	2.306	0.934
Contribution to variability (%)	68.80	14.30
Total	variability 68.80	83.60

^aSTI = salinity tolerance indexes. Ht = seedling height, RL = root length, FM = seedling fresh matter, and DM = seedling dry matter.

Based on the first two components, cultivars were placed in four groups (see figure), where the variability in cultivar response to salinity was observed. Group I (Caribe 1, IA Cuba-26,2 196, Ecia 22-8, J-